

Povezani odprti podatki (LOD) v praksi

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O projektu ARIADNE

**Advanced
Research
Infrastructure for
Archaeological
Dataset
Networking in
Europe**

O projektu ARIADNE

- 4 letni projekt projekt (začetek 02/2013)
- OP7 - “Integrating Activity”
- 6.5m €
- Koordinatorja
 - Prof. Franco Niccolucci, Univerza Firenze
 - Prof. Julian Richards, Univerza York
- www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu

O projektu ARIADNE

- 24 partnerjev, 18 držav
- 15 pridruženih partnerjev
- Odprto partnerstvo
- Gradimo skupnost
 - “Trans national access”
 - Delavnice
 - Interesne skupine

O projektu ARIADNE

- ARIADNE je osredotočena na arheološko snovno dediščino
 - želimo preseči fragmentacijo repozitorijev arheoloških podatkov
 - spodbujamo kulturo deljenja in pre-uporabe podatkov
- Imamo skupne točke z digitalnim humanizmom in drugimi raziskovalnimi infrastrukturami

O projektu ARIADNE

- Omogočiti raziskovalcem enostaven in nadzorovan spletni dostop do:
 - Podatkov in podatkovnih zbirk
 - Spletnih storitev
 - Orodij za sodelovanje
- Preseči politične in institucionalne meje

O projektu ARIADNE

- Mobilizirati
- Integrirati
- Narediti dostopno

Vaši podatki

Dendrokronološki podatki (DCCD) 5200 vzorcev

INRAP: 27,000 terenskih poročil

SIGECweb: 326,000 arheoloških predmetov

Archaeological Survey of Ireland, 141,000 records

ADS: 36,000 strokovnih poročil, več kot 1000 projektnih arhivov; skupaj 1.3 milijonov zapisov

ARACHNE: 500,000 arheoloških predmetov, zapisov, slik

ZRC-SAZU, 11,000 najdišč

FASTI online: 12,000 poročil o izkopavanjih iz 3,300 najdišč v 14 državah

Povezovanje podatkov

- Povezujemo podatke v številnih (naravnih) jezikih in standardih
- ARIADNE za integracijo podatkov uporablja CIDOC CRM z dodatkom za arheologijo
 - Obstoječi podatki so mapirani na “ARIADNE data model”
 - Koncepti so mapirani na Getty AAT tezaver

Povezovanje podatkov

ARIADNE Users Framework

All fields ▾ tumul

tumuli / tumuli / tumulus ⓘ

Welcome

ARIADNE brings together and integrates existing archaeological research data infrastructures so that researchers can use the various distributed datasets and new and powerful technologies as an integral component of the archaeological research methodology.

Browse the Catalog

Where

When

What

farmhouses

archaeology cairns fosse

Church

burials

pits (earthworks)

- Pojmi iz “Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus” (AAT) kot ponujeni pojmi
 - Omogoča razširitev poizvedbe
 - Večjezična podpora (brez Slovenščine, samo “veliki” jeziki)

[Catalog](#)[Services](#)[About](#)

tumuli

Getty AAT ID 300391495

Note Ancient sepulchral mounds, particularly those created by the Bronze Age Tumulus culture evident in Europe from around 1600 BCE.

URI <http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300391495>

Broader burial mounds

Connected resources

Search connected resources **354**

Terms

English

tumuli

tumulus

Provider mapping

Tumulus

Match URI <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#closeMatch>

Source URI <http://www.fastionline.org/concept/attribute/tumulus>

gomila (neopredelje...

Match URI <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#closeMatch>

Source URI <http://tempuri/aat-mappings-zrc-sazu-arkas/gomila%20%28neopredeljena%29>

gomilno grobišče

Match URI <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#broadMatch>

Source URI <http://tempuri/aat-mappings-zrc-sazu-arkas/gomilno%20grobi%C5%A1%C4%8De>

Tumulus

Match URI <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#exactMatch>

Source URI <http://tempuri/DAI/Tumulus>

The screenshot shows the ARIADNE Portal search results for the query 'tumuli'. The interface includes a search bar at the top with the text 'Start a new search...'. Below the search bar, there are navigation links for 'Catalog', 'Services', and 'About'. The search results are displayed in a list format, with a total of 1,290 results. The results are sorted by 'Score'. The first three results are highlighted in a light blue box. A blue callout box points to the 'Resource type' field in the first result, listing various subject types: Native Subject, Keyword, Contributor, Publisher, Place, and Dating. The 'When' filter shows a histogram of results over time, with a peak around 0 AD. The 'Where' filter shows a map of Europe with highlighted regions. The 'Resource type' filter is expanded to show 'Sites and monuments databases or inventories' with 926 results.

Start a new search...

Catalog Services About

Total results: 1,290

Order By Score

Current search:

Filters

Where

When

Resource type

Sites and monuments databases or inventories 926

Bailar Kairyak Tumuli 2010
Type: Event/intervention resources Publisher: International Association for Classical Archaeology
Fasti record for interventions in the year 2010 at Bailar Kairyak Tumuli
Derived Subject: tumuli
resource.aatSubjects.label: tumuli
Derived Subject: tumuli

Isperih Tumuli 2009
Type: Event/intervention resources Publisher: International Association for Classical Archaeology
Fasti record for interventions in the year 2009 at Isperih Tumuli
Derived Subject: tumuli
resource.aatSubjects.label: tumuli

Borisovo Tumuli 2011
Type: Event/intervention resources Publisher: International Association for Classical Archaeology
Fasti record for interventions in the year 2011 at Borisovo Tumuli
Derived Subject: tumuli
resource.aatSubjects.label: tumuli

Ravnishteto Tumuli 2005
Type: Event/intervention resources Publisher: International Association for Classical Archaeology

Resource type
Native Subject
Keyword
Contributor
Publisher
Place
Dating

ARIADNE in PeriodO

- PeriodO je gazetar odprtih povezanih podatkov (LOD gazetteer)
 - Strokovne definicije zgodovinskih, umetnostno-zgodovinskih in arheoloških obdobj
 - Sedaj vsebuja definicije arheoloških obdobj partnerjev ARIADNE
 - Pojmi imajo PeriodO URI naslove
- Omogoča lažje povezovanje podatkov z različno definiranimi obdobji
 - (arheologija = časoprostor)

The screenshot shows the PeriodO web application interface. At the top, it says "PeriodO" and "Current backend: Canonical [switch]". There are "Sign in" and "Menu" buttons. Below that, there are tabs for "Browse by: Period" and "Collection". The main section is titled "Periods" and shows "Viewing 1 - 25 of 3745". There is a "Show" dropdown set to "25" and "periods at a time." Below that are "Previous" and "Next" buttons, and a pagination bar with numbers 1, 2, 3, ..., 149, 150. The main content is a table with columns "Label", "Earliest start", and "Latest stop".

Label	Earliest start	Latest stop
2nd Millenium BCE	-2000	-1000
2nd Millenium BC Egypt (2000-1000 BC)	-2000	-1000
2nd Millenium BC Levant (2000-1000 BC)	-2000	-1000
3rd millennium BC	-3000	-2000
4th millenium BCE	-4000	-3000
13th Century AD Eastern Mediterranean (AD 1200-1300)	1200	1300
16th Century	1500	1600
17th Century	1600	1700
17th Century (1600 - 1699)	1600	1699

On the right side, there are "Filters" and "Text" sections. The "Filters" section has a "Time range" filter with a "Hide outliers?" checkbox and a "Hiding range from -2600000 to -49942" label. Below that is a small area chart. The "Text" section has a "Match string" input field. At the bottom right, there is a "Source" section with a "Reset" button and a list of sources:

- 944 British Museum.
- 659 ARIADNE Consortium. ARIADNE Data Collection. 2015.
- 525 David G. Anderson. Digital Index of North American Archaeology (DINAA). 2012.
- 212 AIAC and L - P : Archaeology. FASTI - Home. 2004.
- 116 Roger Bagnall. Pleiades: A community-built gazetteer and

<http://perio.do/>

ARIADNE visual media service

Create your online showcase for 3d models, images and RTI.

[Upload »](#)

[Browse »](#)

3D models

3D representations produced with 3D scanners or photogrammetry are extremely high-resolution and hard to visualize at interactive rate. This service produces a web page that supports interactive visualization of your data, after converting it into an efficient multiresolution encoding.

[View details »](#)

[Demo](#)

RTI images

Relightable images (called Reflection Transformation Images, RTI, or Polynomial Texture Maps, PTM) are becoming an [increasingly used media](#). This service closes a current gap, giving support for easy publication on the web and interactive visualization of RTI images.

[View details »](#)

[Demo](#)

High-resolution images

High-resolution images are a commodity resource in archaeology. Unfortunately, they are most often disseminated and published on the web by using low-resolution versions (a single 40Mpixel images is 120MB in uncompressed format and around 10MB when lossy compressed).

[View details »](#)

[Demo](#)

<http://visual.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>

Storitve za objavljanje vizualnih medijev

Konverzija podatkov v format primeren za splet olajša spletno objavo oz. vizualizacijo:

- 3R modeli
- Računalniško upodabljanje pretvarjanja odbojnosti (RTI)
- Visokoločljive 2R slike

<http://visual.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>

Storitve za objavljanje vizualnih medijev

Nalaganje lastnih podatkov

- Za vsako enoto uporabnik izpolni enostaven obrazec (metapodatki)
- Izberemo datoteko
- Sprejmemo pogoje (© ostane vaš!)
- Upload!

Upload your media

For the list of supported filetypes see the [help page](#).

Information about you

Email

Name

Institution

Information about the digital object

Label

Title

Description

Tags

Web resource

Collection/Dataset

Copyright owner

Private Keep this object private.

File

I have read and accepted the [usage terms](#).

<http://visual.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>

Storitve za objavljanje vizualnih medijev

- Iskanje z brskanjem

Media

Search...

[3D models](#) [Images](#) [RTI](#)

type	title	size	
	-	111.13 MB	View
	3D model of the Arringatore	80.23 MB	View
	Alchemy high-res image of right-side spiral	44.87 MB	View
	Alchemy high-res image of top-left angle	40.22 MB	View
	Amarna Figurine	28.71 MB	View
	Apollo - Luni Temple.	6.12 MB	View
	Askos	29.23 MB	View
	Askos	128.91 MB	View
	A small bronze horse	26.87 MB	View

<http://visual.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>

Storitve za objavljanje vizualnih medijev

3R modeli:

- 3R model kipa “Frontone A” iz templja Luni, terracota, 2. st. pr. n. št.
- National Archaeological Museum in CNR-ISTI

<http://visual.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/3d/apollo>

Storitve za objavljanje vizualnih medijev

RTI model:

- 46,7 mb
- Bizantinski kovanec
- ISTI-CNR

http://visual.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/rti/testnomprojetmj30052016_02

Storitve za objavljanje vizualnih medijev

Visokoločljive 2D slike:

- 138,2 mb
- Vizualizacija lidarskih podatkov, Gradišče nad Knežakom
- ZRC SAZU

http://visual.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/img/lidar_a

Storitev za prostorske podatke

Landscape Services

Cloud Service

3D Terrain Service

Help

Contacts

ARIADNE

Landscape Services

Landscape Services for **ARIADNE** are a set of responsive web services that include large terrain datasets generation, 3D landscape composing and 3D model processing, leveraging on powerful open-source frameworks and toolkits such as **GDAL**, **OSGjs**, **OpenSceneGraph** and **ownCloud**. Here a few examples of 3D datasets produced by the services:

Cloud Service

This is the main service to **access**, **manage** and eventually **share** your online data. This includes DEM input data, Geo-images, 3D models, etc.

Cloud Service

3D Terrain Service

You can use this service to process DEM, geo-images and shapefiles to produce large 3D terrain Datasets optimised for real-time visualization and web streaming.

3D Terrain Service

Terrain Gallery

View, download or delete your generated 3D Terrain datasets. You can also interactively explore a 3D dataset online and present it in your web site, through desktop browsers, smartphones or tablets.

Terrain Gallery

<http://landscape.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>

Ariadne, princesa Krete, hči kralja Minosa in kraljice Faziphae.

Ko se je Tezej, sinj kralja Egeja, javil, da ubije Minotavra, se je Ariadne vanj zaljubila na prvi pogled. Pomagala mu je ubiti Minotavra tako, da mu je podarila čarobni meč za boj z Minotavrom ter klobčič niti, s pomočjo katerega se mu bo uspelo rešiti iz labirinta.

Hvala za pozornost

e-pošta: info@ariadne-infrastructure.eu

<http://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu>

<http://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu>

Twitter: @ariadne-infrastructure

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